

REPORT ON NON-SCIENTIFIC DISSEMINATION

[Deliverable 8.3]

ER4STEM - EDUCATIONAL ROBOTICS FOR STEM

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Inhalt

1	Executive Summary	4
1.1	Role, Purpose and Objectives of the Deliverable	4
1.2	Correlation to Other ER4STEM Deliverables	4
1.3	Structure of This Document.....	4
2	Introduction.....	5
3	General dissemination activities	6
3.1	Activities within the First Year	6
3.2	Activities within the Second Year	23
3.3	Activities within the Third Year.....	54
4	Web and social media dissemination activities.....	77
5	Conclusion	96

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

DOCUMENT REVISION HISTORY

Version Number	Date	Description	Author
V1	23.08.2018	Draft version	Wilfried Lepuschitz
V2	30.08.2018	Reviewed version	Ivaylo Gueorguiev
V3	30.08.2018	Final version	Wilfried Lepuschitz

CONTRIBUTORS

Name	Beneficiary	Section affected	Date of 1st contribution
Wilfried Lepuschitz	PRIA	all	
Angele Giuliano	AcrossLimits	AL sections	
Christina Todorova	ESI CEE	ESI CEE section	
Ivaylo Gueorguiev	ESI CEE	ESI CEE sections; Peer Review	
Pavel Varbanov	ESI CEE	ESI CEE sections	
Julia Angel-Fernandez	TU Wien	TU Wien sections	
Patrick Harner	TU Wien	TU Wien sections	
Carina Girvan	Cardiff University	CU sections	
Sarah Hopkins-Weaver	Cardiff University	CU sections	
Chronis Kynigos	University of Athens	UoA sections	
Marianthi Grizioti	University of Athens	UoA sections	
Miroslav Štola	Certicon	Introduction, Certicon section	

DISCLAIMER

This Deliverable reflects only the author's view. Neither the author(s) nor the REA are responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

1.1 ROLE, PURPOSE AND OBJECTIVES OF THE DELIVERABLE

The purpose of this document is the collection and description of non-scientific dissemination activities.

1.2 CORRELATION TO OTHER ER4STEM DELIVERABLES

ER4STEM was presented in a few events organized or hosted by Scientix. These activities are not described in this deliverable but can be found in the specific Scientix-related deliverable D8.4 and also in D5.4 concerning the repository workshop.

Also any workshop or student conference organized within the frame of ER4STEM represents a non-scientific dissemination event but as they are integral parts of WP2 and WP3, only awareness activities are mentioned in this document but the events or information regarding those events are mentioned in the deliverables of WP2 and WP3.

1.3 STRUCTURE OF THIS DOCUMENT

Section 2 introduces the table structure used for the general activities, which are presented in Section 3. Section 4 then gives an overview on the web and social media activities related to ER4STEM. This document is then concluded in Section 5.

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

2 INTRODUCTION

Information about the ER4STEM project has been disseminated in numerous non-scientific activities of all partners. For describing general activities, e.g. events or specific workshops not performed within WP2, the following table structure is used. Also images are provided for some of the events below the event table description.

Sample Table for General Activities:

Date	Date of the event
General Description	Set the background of the event.
Multimedia	Links for audio, video, photo or storage.
Target Audience	Describe the target audience by the means of their age or any other trait that links the audience. If not specified, fill in "Not specified".
Feedback / Impact	Was there any feedback? Questions from audience, letters, comments on social media. Or impact e.g. subsequent articles, reviews or other.
Language	Used language
Local/Global	Did the event take place locally (local physical event, local newspaper, ...) or global (international papers, internet, ...).
Organizer/Other involved parties	Who is the organizer? Were there other parties involved?
Activity Type	Web page/Article/Blog post/Social media post/Lecture/Convention/...
URL	Specify URL of the event if any.
Comments/Summary	Summary plus any additional info that did not fit into previous cells.

Exemplary web or social media activities are described in textual form with additional images, e.g. screenshots.

In all the cases the ER4STEM partners mentioned the project. The materials given to the participants include information about ER4STEM project key attributes including the funding provided by the EU.

In total, more than 40 activities for non-scientific dissemination in more than 10 countries were conducted by the project partners for promoting ER4STEM.

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

3 GENERAL DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

3.1 ACTIVITIES WITHIN THE FIRST YEAR

AUSTRIA – TU WIEN

ER4STEM stickers are given to the participants. Also ER4STEM is mentioned during meetings with schools teachers, while they get explanations about the workshops offered and asked if they are willing to participate.

EUROPEAN RESEARCHERS' NIGHT

Date	30.09.2016
General Description	“European Researchers’ Night is a mega event that takes place every year simultaneously in several hundred cities all over Europe and beyond. The key objective of the event is to increase general public awareness of the diversity of scientific research but also promote and facilitate greater public participation in the entire scientific process including participation in scientific research as well as dissemination activities.” from: http://sci4all.eu/
Multimedia	
Target Audience	Children and parents
Feedback / Impact	
Language	German
Local/Global	Local physical event in Vienna, Austria
Organizer/Other involved parties	Practical Robotics Institute Austria was organizer of ERN
Activity Type	Short activities to introduce sequence on programming
URL	http://be-scienced.eu/
Comments/Summary	This was a small activity done in the frame of the European Researchers’ Night.

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

AUSTRIA – PRIA

ER4STEM stickers are given to all participants of workshops conducted by PRIA.

Together with Lara Lammer from Vienna University of Technology, Wilfried Lepuschitz took part at the Scientix events “10th Scientix Projects’ Networking Event” and “10th Science Projects Workshop in the Future Classroom Lab” in Brussels on 26th and 27th February 2016, which is described in more detail in deliverable D8.4.

TEACHERS’ WORKSHOP AT ECER 2016

Date	11.04.2016
General Description	A workshop for the attending teachers of ECER 2016 in Vienna was carried out as replacement of the originally planned Scientix teachers panel workshop (see also D8.4).
Multimedia	
Target Audience	Teachers attending ECER
Feedback / Impact	The findings from this workshop were instrumental to be able to define the Use Case scenario for the creation of the ER4STEM repository especially from the point of view of a teacher. Various needs were identified.
Language	English
Local/Global	Local physical event in Vienna, Austria
Organizer/Other involved parties	Organizers: PRIA and TU Wien
Activity Type	Presentation and discussion about requirements and expectations regarding ER4STEM framework and repository
URL	
Comments/Summary	This event

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

**Educational Robotics for Science,
Technology, Engineering and Mathematics**

Organized as part of European
Conference in Educational
Robotics ECER2016

Teacher Workshop

„Teachers' requirements to incorporate educational
robotics activities in a classroom“

Active 2-hour workshop based on the world café concept where teachers
discuss pros and cons in smaller groups, and present to all participants their
requirements for the ER4STEM framework and repository

Date: 11 April 2016, 15:00
Place: TGM, Vienna
Contact: Wilfried Lepuschitz
lepuschitz@pria.at

Participation is
free of charge

er4stem.com
f ER4STEM
@er4stem

The project has received funding from the European
Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program
under grant agreement No. 665972

DIGITALE KOMPETENZEN 4.0

Date	24.05.2016
General Description	Wilfried Lepuschitz of PRIA was invited for holding a presentation on how to motivate and prepare future scientists and engineers in robotics and ICT. Furthermore, he took part in the following panel discussion. Besides, 3 more presentations (1 from an educational robotics company, 2 from schools) were given and the presenters also took part in the panel discussion.
Multimedia	
Target Audience	Companies interested in possibilities to foster digital competences in schools
Feedback / Impact	The audience was interested in the topic educational robotics but no further outcome can be reported..
Language	German
Local/Global	Local physical event in Vienna, Austria
Organizer/Other involved parties	Organizers: Vienna Business Agency (funding agency), Verband Österreichischer Software Industrie

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

Activity Type	Presentation including an overview on the project ER4STEM, panel discussion
URL	https://www.facebook.com/events/1002156513211564/
Comments/Summary	The event was a good chance to present educational robotics in general and ER4STEM to interested companies. For them it was understandable why robotics is such a good tool for fostering the children’s interest in STEM.

MALTA – ACROSSLIMITS

ER4STEM project information was disseminated in general events that the company organises including the mention of the project during our training sessions which targets teacher and educators across Europe.

ADVERT IN “THE SUNDAY TIMES OF MALTA”

Date	January-March 2016
General Description	An advert was placed in a local English newspaper, The Sunday Times of Malta, which has a very high number of Sunday readers (and also the advert was placed on social media). This advert

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

	published the expression of interest to invite schools which were interested in participating to our workshops.
Multimedia	
Target Audience	Maltese schools
Feedback / Impact	Many schools answered and became our pool of contacts throughout the project in order to run workshops with them
Language	English
Local/Global	National
Organizer/Other involved parties	AcrossLimits
Activity Type	Newspaper advert
URL	http://www.timesofmalta.com
Comments/Summary	Copies of the adverts published are reproduced below

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

UK – CARDIFF UNIVERSITY

Awareness raising activities: Discussion with leading organisations which work with teachers and schools including the National STEM Learning Centre (UK), TechnoCamps (Wales), Education Workforce Council Wales, WiseKids and Lead Creative Schools.

The Lead Creative Schools programme in Wales will implement the Activity Plan (WP4) and integrate aspects of the ER4STEM evaluation (WP6) with their own workshop evaluation in 2017.

BULGARIA – ESI CEE

ESI CEE popularized the activities under ER4STEM project through three main channels - externally organized events (conferences, workshops, workgroups etc.), web/ social/ e-mail/ traditional media, and face-to-face meetings with partners and clients.

TECHNICAL CONFERENCE INDEED WE CAN OF MICROSOFT

Date	10/21/2015
General Description	<p>Presentation held by Ivaylo Gueorguiev during the technical conference INDEED WE CAN of Microsoft, 20-21 October 2015 in Sofia, Bulgaria about the ER4STEM project activities, with a focus on educational robotics workshops held in Bulgaria, as well as ECER.</p> <p>Since the beginning of the project in October 2015 ESI CEE started to contact potential partners, contributors and beneficiaries. In October 2015, the team of ESI CEE was invited to present the project in INDEED 2015 the biggest Microsoft conference in Sofia with participation of more than 100 schoolteachers, IT professionals and companies. Ivaylo Gueorguiev presented the project in 20 min. and attracted interest of more than 20 schoolteachers. ESI CEE team made the follow up with interested schools and obtained commitment for ERWs organizing from 10 school directors. In December 2015, Ivaylo Gueorguiev and George Sharkov presented the project in the annual meeting of management and executives of Bulgarian IT companies, members of the Bulgarian Association of Software Companies (BASSCOM). In the period November 2015-February 2016, the team of ESI CEE had more than 15 direct meetings with directors and management of Bulgarian primary and secondary schools.</p>
Multimedia	

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

Target Audience	Representatives and decision-makers from schools, education specialists, pedagogues and teachers
Feedback / Impact	School principals and teachers signed up for news about the project, providing ESI CEE team with contact details. Some of them expressed interest to conduct educational robotics workshops in their schools. A representative from the Vocational High School of Electronics “John Atanasoff” in Sofia expressed interest in ECER and scheduled a meeting with school board and school students.
Language	Bulgarian
Local/Global	Local physical event at Arena Mladost, Sofia, Bulgaria
Organizer/Other involved parties	European Software Institute – Center Eastern Europe (ESI CEE)
Activity Type	Presentation on the ER4STEM project activities and dissemination of promotional materials.
URL	http://computerworld.bg/48254_majkrosoft_balgariya_obyavi_konferenciyata_indeed_we_can
Comments/Summary	The presentation mainly focused on opportunities for participating in educational robotics workshops but nevertheless began with a presentation of the project, its philosophy and main goals. As the conference was attended by numerous teachers, school principals and representatives, those who were interested in participating had the opportunity to ask their questions and sign up for receiving more information. ECER was also presented as many of the participants were representing technical schools. After the event, ESI CEE still maintains contacts with some of the participants and has conducted educational robotics workshops in 3 schools, represented during the Microsoft event.

TUES ECER 2016 & ER4STEM PRESENTATION

Date	12/10/2015
------	------------

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

General Description	<p>Presentation of ER4STEM and the ECER Conference in April 2016 in Sofia, Bulgaria at the Technical School “Electronic Systems”</p> <p>The event was followed up by a formation of a school team for the BotBall competition at ECER 2016.</p>
Multimedia	<p>http://www.elsys-bg.org/blog/article/information-meeting-with-robots-demonstration-2015/</p>
Target Audience	<p>High school students from Technical School “Electronic Systems” and their teachers</p>
Feedback / Impact	<p>Students signed up to apply for entering the school team for the BotBall competition. Teachers were enthusiastic that students have the opportunity to represent their school and Bulgaria at ECER for the first time.</p> <p>The school is a technical gymnasium that participates in robotic competitions and activities in the field and is a believer in the educational benefits of robotics. They were obviously interested to participate at ECER.</p>
Language	<p>Bulgarian</p>
Local/Global	<p>Local physical event at the Technical School “Electronic Systems”</p> <p>2 “Vladimir Pashov” Str., Sofia, Bulgaria</p>
Organizer/Other involved parties	<p>European Software Institute – Center Eastern Europe (ESI CEE)</p>
Activity Type	<p>Presentation, demonstrations and dissemination of promotional materials about ER4STEM project and the ECER conference.</p>
URL	<p>http://www.elsys-bg.org/blog/article/information-meeting-with-robots-demonstration-2015/</p>

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

Comments/Summary	<p>During the TUES Inspiration Talks, ESI CEE team and a NAO humanoid robot presented ER4STEM project activities and engaged students in discussions on how robots inspire, help you learn and improve your professional opportunities. ECER was presented by ESI CEE and the RoboLeague of Bulgaria.</p> <p>Students had the opportunity to ask questions about the competition. The school announced criteria for selection for the school team and how to apply.</p>
------------------	---

I, ENGINEER 2016

Date	03/11/2016
General Description	<p>I, Engineer is an annually organized event for teachers and students, primarily for high school students from technical schools from all over Bulgaria. It offers robotics competitions, exhibitions, workshops and presentations.</p> <p>ER4STEM was promoted among teachers and students by the ESI CEE team and friends, by organizing a free workshop for students. During the workshop, the esTank, the Arduino-based educational robotics kit, specially developed by ESI CEE for work with children, was applied for the workshop. Students got the chance to build a robot and then program it, and their teachers were supporting and observing their students' work.</p> <p>Before and after the workshop, the ER4STEM project was presented, both by the ESI CEE team and by the organizers of the event, and the workshop was presented as part of the educational technology developed under the ER4STEM project.</p>
Multimedia	http://iengineer.bg/2016/
Target Audience	School and university students, teachers, parents. Presentation on the benefits of integrating educational robotics as an instrument for teaching general education subjects was held before teachers and school representatives.

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

Feedback / Impact	The target audience of teachers and parents were interested in the presentation of the project and the application of educational robotics in the educational process. Children were attracted to the robots and were interested in the technology demonstrations and the talks about different few robots and robot applications. The audience was generally interested; people came to ask questions about the project and how to get involved. Children were asking lots of questions about robots and technology and seemed to be really fascinated by the idea that they are going to be the creators of the future robots.
Language	Bulgarian
Local/Global	Local physical event at the InterExpo Center, Sofia 147 "Tsarigradsko Shosse" Blvd.
Organizer/Other involved parties	WishBox (http://wishbox.org/) Inter Expo Center (https://iec.bg/index.php/bg/) ABC Systems (http://abcsystems.bg) others, full list of partners is available at http://iengineer.bg/2016/
Activity Type	Presentations and an educational robotics workshop, as well as dissemination of promotional materials about ER4STEM project
URL	http://iengineer.bg/2016/
Comments/Summary	The local organizers of the event assessed the ESI CEE panel as successful. The demonstrations and presentations attracted a mixed audience. The event was useful to raise awareness on the project and more generally, on benefits of the integration of educational robotics mechanisms in education. Promotional materials were disseminated and many school representatives were interested in getting contact information. High school students were informed about the upcoming edition of ECER and were further made aware that the following edition of ECER in 2017 (it was way too late to sign up for Vienna's 2016 edition of ECER) will be in Sofia, Bulgaria and that they could participate in it as a team.

VARNA FREE UNIVERSITY ER4STEM PRESENTATION

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

Date	03/12/2016 – 03/13/2016
General Description	<p>ESI CEE was invited by the Varna Free University to attend an educational event in Varna, Bulgaria. The event targeted primarily primary school teachers and put a strong focus on how technology could be integrated to bring value to education in general.</p> <p>ESI CEE took this opportunity to present the ER4STEM project, make contacts with Bulgarian teachers from Varna and the cities nearby and inform them on how they could benefit by the ER4STEM projects, including the upcoming release of the repository for educational robotics materials, the activity plans that were to be released and the pedagogical theory, underlying the ER4STEM project. We also presented some data obtained by the workshops, organized in Bulgaria and our opinions and observations as tutors, on the impact of the educational robotics activities on the students. We also made a demonstration with the NAO robot for both the teachers and the students present.</p> <p>We further continued the demonstration with an educational robotics workshop, which was attended by the teacher and their students. This workshop was included in the ER4STEM workshops in project year 1 and was standardly evaluated.</p>
Multimedia	<p>https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Hlk-W_2kUI4</p> <p>Blogpost by a School Teacher, who's students attended both the I, Engineer event on the previous day, and the workshop at Varna Free University</p>
Target Audience	School teachers and their students. Presentations, demonstrations and an educational robotics workshop.
Feedback / Impact	Both teachers and students were interested in the presentations, demonstrations and the workshop. ESI CEE took up the initiative to inform them on the release of the ER4STEM repository on educational robotics as well as about upcoming events on educational robotics, that are intended for teachers and educators. We were asked a lot of questions on the feedback received from students throughout this first year of the project, and also teachers were interested on the attitude of our teachers towards activities such as this one.

Language	Bulgarian
Local/Global	Physical event at Varna Free University, Varna, Bulgaria 111-B “Tsarigradsko Shosse” Blvd.
Organizer/Other involved parties	Varna Free University European Software Institute – Center Eastern Europe (ESI CEE)
Activity Type	Presentations and an educational robotics workshop, as well as dissemination of promotional materials about ER4STEM project
URL	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Hlk-W_2kUI4 Blogpost by a School Teacher, who’s students attended both the I, Engineer event on the previous day, and the workshop at Varna Free University
Comments/Summary	The local organizers of the event assessed the ESI CEE panel as successful. The demonstrations and presentations attracted a mixed audience. The event was useful to raise awareness on the project and more generally, on benefits of the integration of educational robotics mechanisms in education.

EUROPEAN RESEARCHERS’ NIGHT

Date	09/30/2016
General Description	<p>During the European Researchers’ Night, ESI CEE participated with a presentation on why educational robotics is important as well as demonstrations with the humanoid robot NAO and the robot for educational purposes Finch. As the event was attended by school representatives, ER4STEM was promoted during the presentation as a great opportunity for schools to get more involved in educational robotics, followed by other presentations on curious applications of robotics.</p> <p>Promotional materials were handed out with project information and contacts of the local partner.</p>

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

Multimedia	https://www.facebook.com/plugins/video.php?href=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.facebook.com%2FSofiaTechPark%2Fvideos%2F1289425597755668%2F&
Target Audience	School and university students, teachers, parents. Presentation on the benefits of integrating educational robotics as an instrument for teaching general education subjects was held before teachers and school representatives.
Feedback / Impact	The target audience of teachers and parents were interested in the presentation of the project and the application of educational robotics in the educational process. Children were attracted to the robots and were interested in the technology demonstrations and the talks about different robots and robot applications. The audience was generally interested, few people came to ask questions about the project and how to get involved. Children were asking lots of questions about robots and technology and seemed to be really fascinated by the idea that they are going to be the creators of the future robots.
Language	Bulgarian
Local/Global	Local physical event at the Laboratory Complex at Sofia Tech Park 111-B “Tsarigradsko Shosse” Blvd.
Organizer/Other involved parties	European Software Institute – Center Eastern Europe (ESI CEE)
Activity Type	Presentation and demonstration, as well as dissemination of promotional materials about ER4STEM project
URL	http://events.codeweek.eu/view/12587/er4stem-educational-robotics-workshop/
Comments/Summary	The local organizers of the event assessed the ESI CEE panel as successful. The demonstrations and presentations attracted a great crowd of mixed audience. The event was useful to raise awareness on the project and more generally, on benefits of the integration of educational robotics mechanisms in education. Promotional materials were disseminated and a lot of school representatives were interested in getting contact information.

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

GREECE – UOA

SUMMER CAMP ACTIVITY

Date	4-8 July 2016
General Description	Educational Robotics Workshops were organized as part of a Summer Camp at the Industrial Gas Museum in Athens (July 2016). Each workshop had duration 4 hours and it was divided into 4 days (1 hour/day). 3 workshops were organized with 25 children each aged 5- 11 years old. Children played with Lego Wedo 2.0 and Lego NXT, building and programming their own robots. Younger children focused on building funny constructions and giving them life by selecting move, sound and light and older children focused on programming autonomous robot's behaviors.
Multimedia	
Target Audience	Children (5-11 years old), Parents

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

Feedback / Impact	Children were quite interested in robotics and participated with great enthusiasm in the workshop. Many of the children didn't have any previous experience with Educational Robotics workshops so they got familiar with how robots work. Some of them expressed interest to participate in similar robotics activities in the future. Some of the parents and also the summer Camp organizers and tutors asked information about ER4STEM project
Language	Greek
Local/Global	The workshops were organized in the Technopolis City of Athens venue (http://www.technopolis-athens.com/web/guest/museum/home)
Organizer/Other involved parties	The workshops were organized by Educational Technology Lab UoA The summer camp was organized by Technopolis City of Athens and the Industrial Gas Museum,
Activity Type	Hands-on Workshops with Lego Wedo 2.0 and Lego NXT
URL	http://www.technopolis-athens.com/web/guest/events/~eventsbrowser/16343/7202/0/0?p_p_action=1&bs_events_browser_loadaction=view&bs_events_browser_eventStartDate=21%2F06%2F2016&bs_events_browser_eventEndDate=15%2F07%2F2016&bs_events_browser_redirect=%2Fweb%2Fguest%2Fevents%2F~%2Ftopic%2F7202& Industrial Gas Museum website
Comments/Summary	

CZECH REPUBLIC – CERTICON

EU CODEWEEK

Date	10/20/2016-10/21/2016
------	-----------------------

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

General Description	Annual EU code week event that tries to attract young people to programming. Certicon prepared an event for this year code week.
Multimedia	Online learning application video: https://drive.google.com/open?id=0B7j5mGBaUrPUWkluT1VVNHB5S28 Hand written digits recognition: https://drive.google.com/open?id=0B7j5mGBaUrPUS3YxUEVB UWZxSWs
Target Audience	Our event was intended for high school and early undergraduate students. In total, there were three sessions with the total of 30 students.
Feedback / Impact	There was a positive feedback from all three groups. It was clear we showed them a fascinating subject very much different from conventional programming. The students were very attentive which was clear from the amount of raised questions and their ongoing interest.
Language	Czech
Local/Global	Locally at Certicon headquarters in Prague
Organizer/Other involved parties	Certicon a.s.
Activity Type	Seminary about machine learning mainly focused on artificial neural networks used for recognition followed by demonstrations with interactive application. There were three posts. The first featured a computer equipped with camera and a program that could classify hand written digits. The second contained a program, where students first recorded three objects of interest, trained a neural network for those objects and then test how successful is the trained network at recognizing the given objects. The last stand contained videos of our computer vision department.
URL	http://events.codeweek.eu/view/18109/neuronove-site-naprogramuj-si-umelou-inteligenci/saved/
Comments/Summary	The students were very eager and curious. The event was a definite success.

3.2 ACTIVITIES WITHIN THE SECOND YEAR

AUSTRIA – TU WIEN

MAKER FAIRE

Date	May, 20. 2017
General Description	As part of the workshop series at the „Maker Faire 2017“ we did a modified version of the workshop which takes less time and teaches the participants what robots and technology means. First thing has been a coding example on the robot Thymio to program a maze path into the robot via 4 direction buttons. After that we did a few exercises with assistance via a screen to show them quickly what the task is and only a small task for them to think about has been left over.
Multimedia	5 Laptops, 5 Mazes, 10 Thymios (only 5 needed, but ist good to have more for kids which are late)
Target Audience	8-12 years old
Feedback / Impact	The workshop has been great for the kids, they loved it and the tasks have been good to be solved for them. The date early in the morning is a little tricky how much participants are going to be there as they are not subscribed to any workshop and they come when the workshop starts.
Language	German
Local/Global	Local
Organizer/Other involved parties	TU Wien/ER4Stem
Activity Type	Simple programming via touchbuttons, programming with VPL in Thymio Studio
URL	https://makerfairevienna.com/workshop
Comments/Summary	Feedback on the workshop was very good. The only negative thing was that ist very unclear how much kids will attend as they just attend while they are on the maker faire with „first come first sever“ principal. Thats fixed from the organizers.

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

SCHOOL INVITATION

Date	15.05.2017
General Description	The elementary school in the „Lange Gasse“ organized for the first a science day for the whole school. There have been different exercises on different floors including robotics, handcrafts, etc. To expand the range of tasks for this project, members from the ER4STEM TU Vienna team have been asked to join the workshop.
Multimedia	10 Thymio, 10 maze designs A1, Laptop and USB Hub.
Target Audience	7-10 year old
Feedback / Impact	The feedback from the organizers was very positive, thankful and convinced to invite the TU Vienna again for the science day.
Language	German
Local/Global	Local (politicians, parents, media/press and teachers published the attendance)
Organizer/Other involved parties	Teachers from elementary school „Lange Gasse“ (Margit Oudejans)
Activity Type	The exercise which has been presented was the maze design where a Thymio robot has to be guided threw with multiple presses in advance.
URL	
Comments/Summary	This activity was a great opportunity to show a big audience, that engineering and robotics can be easy to operate and fun to play with. It should be considered to attend this workshop again in 2018.

AUSTRIA – PRIA

SCIENCE WITH AND FOR SOCIETY 2017 BROKERAGE EVENT

Date	10.03.2017
------	------------

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

General Description	The brokerage event was of relevance to members of the Science with and for Society research community who are looking for networking and funding opportunities within Horizon 2020. Wilfried Lepuschitz took part as representative from PRIA and the project ER4STEM.
Multimedia	
Target Audience	Stakeholders interested in the Science with and for Society Programme of Horizon 2020
Feedback / Impact	The description of ER4STEM in bilateral talks was of interest and thus valuable connections to other research institutes could be obtained
Language	German
Local/Global	Local physical event in Brussels, Belgium
Organizer/Other involved parties	Organizers: SiS.net2, APRE – Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea, National Documentation Centre / NHRF, KPK PB UE - Krajowy Punkt Kontaktowy Programów Badawczych Unii Europejskiej
Activity Type	Bilateral talks
URL	https://www.b2match.eu/horizon-swafs2017
Comments/Summary	Having the background of the successful project ER4STEM eased the talks with prospective further EU project partners. Consequently, the research network of PRIA was extended.

DIGITALE KOMPETENZEN 4.0 - UND DANN?

Date	27.03.2017
General Description	Likewise to the event “Digitale Kompetenzen 4.0” in 2016 in Vienna, Wilfried Lepuschitz of PRIA was invited for holding a presentation on how to motivate and prepare future scientists and engineers in robotics and ICT at this successor event in Graz, Austria.. Furthermore, he took part in the following panel discussion. Besides, 3 more presentations (1 from a educational robotics company, 2 from schools) were given and the presenters also took part in the panel discussion.
Multimedia	
Target Audience	Companies interested in possibilities to foster digital competences in schools
Feedback / Impact	The audience was interested in the topic educational robotics

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

	but no further outcome can be reported..
Language	German
Local/Global	Local physical event in Graz, Austria
Organizer/Other involved parties	Organizers: Styrian Economic Chamber, Verband Österreichischer Software Industrie, IT Community Styria
Activity Type	Presentation including an overview on the project ER4STEM, panel discussion
URL	https://wirtschaftszeit.at/fileadmin/user_upload/Digitale-Kompetenzen.pdf
Comments/Summary	The event was a good chance to present educational robotics in general and ER4STEM to interested companies. For them it was understandable why robotics is such a good tool for fostering the children's interest in STEM.

MALTA – ACROSSLIMITS

WORKSHOPS AT ST. CATHERINE'S SCHOOL

Date	July 2017 - October 2017
General Description	<p>On the 20th July 2017, AcrossLimits was invited to talk to St. Catherine's School, Pembroke students attending summer school about Robotics during the "Invention Week". During this day, a brief introduction about Robots and Science was given followed by an interactive workshop and hands-on experience using Dash and Dot.</p> <p>Moreover in October we were also part of the EU Code week where we have once more collaborated with St Catherine's School and taught the students there the joy of coding for robotics using Dash and Dot. A video was created by the ESkills Malta Foundation which featured our workshop amongst others held in Malta in that same week.</p>
Multimedia	
Target Audience	Maltese school children and parents
Feedback / Impact	General awareness raising on the project

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

Language	English
Local/Global	Local
Organizer/Other involved parties	AcrossLimits and eSkills Malta Foundation
Activity Type	Video of Workshops
URL	https://eskills.org.mt/en/Pages/Home.aspx
Comments/Summary	A screenshot from the eSkills video showing our workshop is shown below.

MEETINGS WITH STAKEHOLDERS

Date	October 2016 - September 2017
General Description	ER4STEM presentation was also given to colleagues from all over Europe during any meetings that were held in 2017 at AcrossLimits premises or abroad. When our team presents itself, we always show a Powerpoint Presentation and we have a screen dedicated to ER4STEM since many people find the project area fascinating. During 2017 there were 6 such meetings with around 15 to 20 participants each that were held.

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

Multimedia	
Target Audience	European stakeholders and project partners
Feedback / Impact	General awareness raising on the project
Language	English
Local/Global	Global
Organizer/Other involved parties	AcrossLimits
Activity Type	Presentations
URL	
Comments/Summary	Photos from some presentations in our offices and abroad below

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

UK – CARDIFF UNIVERSITY

DIGITAL RESPONSIBILITY

Date	15/12/2016
General Description	<p>Event on Digital Responsibility held at Cardiff University for teachers in Wales to raise awareness of key issues and approaches for teachers. At this presentation Dr Carina Girvan presented the ER4STEM project and explained how it fits with current Welsh Government policy.</p> <p>Presentation to ~25 teachers from across Wales from primary and secondary schools. The presentation included information about the ER4STEM project and how it aligns with Welsh Government's education priorities, particularly the new Digital Competence Framework. In addition there was a demonstration of SLurtle robotics and an invitation for teachers interested to contact Dr Girvan.</p>
Multimedia	

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

Target Audience	Primary and secondary school teachers in Wales
Feedback / Impact	Following the event, three teachers who attended requested further information and participated in the SLurtle robotics workshops in Years 2 and 3.
Language	English
Local/Global	Local, Cardiff University, Wales
Organizer/Other involved parties	Dr Carina Girvan, Cardiff University. Event funded by the British Academy.
Activity Type	Presentation on the ER4STEM project activities
URL	http://computerworld.bg/48254_majkrosoft_balgariya_obyavi_konferenciyat_a_indeed_we_can
Comments/Summary	The presentation mainly focused on opportunities for participating in educational robotics workshops using SLurtles but nevertheless began with a presentation of the project, its philosophy and main goals.

BULGARIA – ESI CEE

EUROPEAN CODE WEEK

Date	10/19/2016 – 10/26/2016
General Description	An educational robotics workshop, which was held in a public school in Sofia, Bulgaria, as part of the European Code Week initiative.

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

Multimedia	<p>https://www.facebook.com/plugins/post.php?href=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.facebook.com%2Fesicenter.bg%2Fposts%2F1703020920018644%3A0&</p> <p>Additional multimedia available offline upon request</p>
Target Audience	<p>Elementary school students from public schools.</p> <p>Boys and Girls, age 8-10 (third grade)</p> <p>Students from 125 High School “Boyan Penev”, 3d grade</p>
Feedback / Impact	<p>There was a positive impact from both the target group (students) and their teacher. As children were asked to fill in evaluation forms to evaluate the workshop as well as meet the research goals of the ER4STEM project, data was collected including their satisfaction from the workshop. Students rated their satisfaction from the workshop with 1 to 5 stars. The workshop was rated from the participants with an average of 4.9.</p>
Language	<p>Bulgarian</p>
Local/Global	<p>Local physical event at a public school</p> <p>125 High School “Boyan Penev”</p> <p>1 “Nikola Genadiev” Str., Sofia, Bulgaria</p>
Organizer/Other involved parties	<p>European Software Institute – Center Eastern Europe (ESI CEE)</p>
Activity Type	<p>Educational Robotics Workshop promoting ER4STEM project activity</p>
URL	<p>http://events.codeweek.eu/view/12587/er4stem-educational-robotics-workshop/</p>

Comments/Summary	<p>This workshop uses robotics as a tool to teach skills such as creativity, collaboration and communication skills as well as digital fluency. Workshops are based on the pedagogical principles of constructionism and constructivism. During this educational robotics workshops, students from 125 High School "Boyan Penev" were able to learn the basic concepts of robotics through demonstrations and games with the humanoid robot NAO. Together, with the support of the tutors and through visual instructions, the students assembled an Arduino robot - a tank, that they programmed to perform simple tasks with the visual programming language Scratch. The workshop also included a creativity seminar based on the mind-mapping concept of Tony Buzan, which aims to encourage children to discover additional practical applications of robotics in various fields of science and in everyday life.</p>
------------------	--

TUES ECER 2017 & ER4STEM PRESENTATION

Date	11/18/2016
------	------------

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

General Description	<p>Presentation of ER4STEM and the ECER Conference in April 2017 in Sofia, Bulgaria at the TUES Inspiration Talks</p> <p>The event was followed up by a formation of a school team for the BotBall competition and so far, two team meetings on which ESI CEE team was present.</p> <p>First team meeting: 12/18/2016 (link)</p> <p>Second team meeting: 01/04/2017 (link)</p>
Multimedia	<p>https://www.facebook.com/pg/tues.bg/photos/?tab=album&album_id=1155606524520028</p> <p>http://www.elsys-bg.org/novini-i-sybitija/novini/uchastie-na-otborana-tues-v-ecer-2017-35/</p>
Target Audience	High school students from Technical School “Electronic Systems” and their teachers
Feedback / Impact	<p>Students signed up to apply for entering the school team for the BotBall competition. Teachers invited us for follow-up meetings and other events.</p> <p>The school is a technical gymnasium that participates in robotic competitions and activities in the field and is a believer in the educational benefits of robotics. They were obviously interested to participate for a second year in ECER.</p>
Language	Bulgarian
Local/Global	Local physical event at the Technical School “Electronic Systems” 2 “Vladimir Pashov” Str., Sofia, Bulgaria
Organizer/Other involved parties	European Software Institute – Center Eastern Europe (ESI CEE)
Activity Type	Presentation, demonstrations and dissemination of promotional materials about ER4STEM project and the ECER conference.

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

URL	http://www.elsys-bg.org/blog/article/tues-robotics-demonstration-2016/
Comments/Summary	<p>During the TUES Inspiration Talks, ESI CEE team and the humanoid robot NAO presented ER4STEM project activities and engaged students in discussions on how robots inspire, help you learn and improve your professional opportunities. ECER was presented by ESI CEE with the support of last year’s TUES-Bulgaria team from BotBall.</p> <p>Students had the opportunity to ask the team and ESI CEE about different aspects of the competition. The school announced the criteria for selection for the new team and how to apply.</p> <p>ESI CEE was invited to come at the first team meetings. On both team meetings, ESI CEE gave short talks about process and project management aspects that might be useful for the design phase of the robot.</p>

EU ROBOT WEEK

Date	<p>11/21/2016 – 12/02/2016</p> <p>Workshop 1 – 11/21/2016 & 11/28/2016</p> <p>Workshop 2 – 11/22/2016 & 11/29/2016</p>
------	--

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

	<p>Workshop 3 – 11/24/2016 & 12/01/2016</p> <p>Workshop 4 – 11/25/2016 & 12/02/2016</p>
General Description	A series of four educational robotics workshops, conducted in two 4-hour sessions, which were held in a public school in Sofia, Bulgaria, as part of the European Robotics Week initiative.
Multimedia	
Target Audience	<p>Elementary school students from public schools.</p> <p>Boys and Girls, age 9-11 (fourth grade)</p> <p>Students from 125 High School “Boyan Penev”, 4th grade</p>
Feedback / Impact	There was a positive impact from both the target group (students) and their teacher. As children were asked to fill in evaluation forms to evaluate the workshop as well as meet the research goals of the ER4STEM project, data was collected including their satisfaction from the workshop. Students rated their satisfaction from the workshop with 1 to 5 stars. The workshop was rated from the participants with an average of 4.5.
Language	Bulgarian
Local/Global	<p>Local physical event at a public school</p> <p>125 High School “Boyan Penev”</p> <p>1 “Nikola Genadiev” Str., Sofia, Bulgaria</p>
Organizer/Other involved parties	European Software Institute – Center Eastern Europe (ESI CEE)
Activity Type	Educational Robotics Workshop promoting ER4STEM project activity

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

URL	https://eu-robotics.net/robotics_week/events/index.html?c=bg
Comments/Summary	<p>This workshop uses robotics and programming as a tool to teach mathematics with accordance to national school curriculum for mathematics for the fourth grade.</p> <p>Workshops are based on the pedagogical principles of constructionism and constructivism. During this educational robotics workshops, students from 125 High School "Boyan Penev" were able exercise mathematical concepts, stipulated in the school plan by programming the Finch robot by BirdBrain Technologies. Students were playing different games with gradual complexity to encourage 21st century skills, such as problem solving, communication, collaboration and digital fluency.</p> <p>The workshop was designed as continuation of previous workshops, conducted with the same students to build on their knowledge and deepen their understanding on how robotics could be applied in a regular learning concepts.</p>

KINDERGARTEN VISIT

Date	12/16/2016
General Description	<p>Veda Private Deutsche Schule visit at the Cybersecurity Lab of Sofia Tech Park, Sofia, Bulgaria aiming to engage children's interest in robotics by demonstrations and information about different applications of robotics in everyday life.</p> <p>The event also targeted the kindergarten teachers to inform them about ER4STEM activities and benefits from applying educational robotics as a way to increase children's learning motivation and an instrument to teach other subjects.</p>
Multimedia	https://www.facebook.com/plugins/post.php?href=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.facebook.com%2Fesicenter.bg%2Fposts%2F1739935412993861&
Target Audience	Kindergarten teachers and kindergarteners from a private kindergarten

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

Feedback / Impact	<p>Children were fascinated about the different robots they were shown and the variety of applications of them in everyday life. They were excited by the idea that someday, when they enter school, robotics might be used as a tool to learn school subjects, as mathematics, which was one of the examples they were demonstrated.</p> <p>For the teachers, it was interesting to observe children’s interest in technology and learn firsthand about possible application of robotics in the learning process. They were provided with more information and promotional materials about the ER4STEM project.</p>
Language	Bulgarian
Local/Global	<p>Local physical event at the Laboratory Complex at Sofia Tech Park</p> <p>111-B “Tsarigradsko Shosse” Blvd.</p>
Organizer/Other involved parties	European Software Institute – Center Eastern Europe (ESI CEE)
Activity Type	<p>Presentation, demonstrations and discussions.</p> <p>Dissemination of promotional materials about ER4STEM project.</p>
URL	https://www.facebook.com/plugins/post.php?href=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.facebook.com%2Fesicenter.bg%2Fposts%2F1739935412993861&
Comments/Summary	<p>Children were engaged in discussions about the “robots of the future” – the robots which they would someday like to build or have in their homes and everyday life. They were demonstrated by the ESI CEE team several robots, including NAO humanoid robot, VGo telepresence robot, a customized research robotic platform and educational robots such as the esrobot Arduino-based tank and the Finch robot by BirdBrain Technologies. They were able to see how robots are programmed to perform certain actions according to their purpose.</p> <p>Teachers were observing the impact that robots, as an educational tool, have on children and had the chance to witness the level of involvement children had during discussions. They were also impressed how much robots made children think about other spheres of life, for instance disabilities and helping people with disabilities with the aid of robots. Teachers were also able to ask their questions regarding the ER4STEM project, the applied pedagogical</p>

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

principles on which the project is build and have some references about useful researches in the field.

MEETING THE NATIONAL SCIENTIX CONTACT POINT

Date	03/23/2017
------	------------

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

General Description	<p>ESI CEE met with Assoc. Prof. Dr. Evgenia Sendova and Konstantin Delchev at the Institute of Mathematics and Informatics at the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (IMI-BAS). IMI-BAS has been nominated and elected as Bulgaria's National Contact Point of Scientix, in partnership with the Center for Creative Training. Coordinator from IMI is Assoc. Prof. Dr. Evgenia Sendova.</p> <p>ESI CEE presented the ER4STEM project, showed workshop videos, activity plans, presented the current state of the ER4STEM framework, generic educational curriculum as well as the ER4STEM repository on educational robotics.</p> <p>ESI CEE presented as well as the upcoming conferences on educational robotics, the European Conference on Educational Robotics (ECER 2017) and the International Conference Robotics in Education (RiE 2017) that were about to take place in Sofia, Bulgaria for the first time within the period 24-28 April 2017.</p>
Target Audience	Scientix Ambassadors
Feedback / Impact	Assoc. Prof. Dr. Evgenia Sendova took upon herself to disseminate information about ER4STEM and the conferences among Scientix Ambassadors in Bulgaria.
Language	Bulgarian
Local/Global	Physical meeting at the IMI-BAS Akad.G.Bonchev Str., Bldg. 8
Organizer/Other involved parties	ESI CEE, IMI-BAS
Activity Type	Meeting, presentation and dissemination of ER4STEM materials
Comments/Summary	We discussed together how Bulgarian teachers, educators as well as Scientix ambassadors might benefit from the ER4STEM project deliverables and products and ESI CEE expressed willingness to support Bulgarian teachers in submitting activity plans within the ER4STEM repository and keep everyone updated on upcoming ER4STEM events.

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

I, ENGINEER 2017

Date	04/06/2017
General Description	<p>I, Engineer is an annually organized event for teachers and students, primarily for high school students from technical schools from all over Bulgaria. It offers robotics competitions, exhibitions, workshops and presentations.</p> <p>This year, ESI CEE had an ER4STEM stand, where we disseminated materials about the project among teachers and we made demonstrations with the humanoid robot NAO.</p>
Multimedia	https://iengineer.bg/
Target Audience	School teachers, students
Feedback / Impact	The teachers who came were interested to learn more about the project as educators who are teaching STEM or are currently implementing robotics in their classrooms. They were interested to learn specifically about the ER4STEM Generic Curricula and the repository on educational robotics activities.
Language	Bulgarian
Local/Global	Local physical event at the InterExpo Center, Sofia 147 "Tsarigradsko Shosse" Blvd.
Organizer/Other involved parties	WishBox (http://wishbox.org/) Inter Expo Center (https://iec.bg/index.php/bg/) ABC Systems (http://abcsystems.bg) others, full list of partners is available at http://iengineer.bg/2016/
Activity Type	Presentations and an educational robotics workshop, as well as dissemination of promotional materials about ER4STEM project
URL	https://iengineer.bg/

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

Comments/Summary	Generally, the event was successful as we got teachers interested into browsing through the ER4STEM repository on educational robotics, once it was up and running and to apply the ER4STEM Generic Curricula to navigate through activity plans.
------------------	---

MOLDOVA TEACHER WORKSHOP

Date	03/08/2017 – 03/09/2017
General Description	<p>ESI CEE was invited by the Moldova Competitiveness Project to share our know-how on educational robotics and present the ER4STEM project and its Generic Curriculum and how it could benefit the teachers. We had a two-day workshop with 30 Moldovan teachers from general education schools, who wanted to integrate STEM within their classroom. There were teachers with very different background – some of them were informatics teachers in advanced classes, others were primary school teachers with a certain fear from technology.</p> <p>During the first day of the workshop, the ESI CEE team presented the ER4STEM project, its work packages and deliverables, which might be of use within the teachers' journey of integrated robotics within their classroom. ESI CEE spoke briefly about the pedagogical technology, underlying the ER4STEM project and presented the activity plan templates that we used to create workshop, which they were to learn. Afterwards, they were familiarized with the workshop, including detailed orchestration of the activity, preparation of the materials, explaining how to install and run all necessary software, how to troubleshoot technology, where to buy replacements. Information about the ER4STEM Repository on Educational Robotics. On the second day, they participated within the workshop, but as students – they went through the workshop process, as a student would, while having the opportunity to ask advanced questions.</p>
Multimedia	http://esirobot.org/workshops - teacher workshops gallery
Target Audience	School teachers
Feedback / Impact	The teachers have already decided that they will include robotics as part of their classroom activities. The teachers were motivated and further gained confidence when they learned about the ER4STEM project and how they could further use the materials, developed under it for their educational purposes.
Language	Bulgarian

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

Local/Global	Local event in Chisinau, Moldova at iHUB 31 August 1989 Street
Organizer/Other involved parties	Ministry of Education of Moldova's Moldova Competitiveness Project, implemented with the support of USAID and the Government of Sweden
Activity Type	A 2-day teacher workshop
URL	https://www.facebook.com/plugins/post.php?href=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.facebook.com%2Fesicenter.bg%2Fposts%2F1790112914642777%3A0&
Comments/Summary	<p>The event was very carefully prepared and carried out. Prior to the actual event, the robotics kits have arrived in Moldova and the team was in close cooperation with a local supporting company, to help them buy and prepare the kits to ensure the ER4STEM standard was met.</p> <p>The event was successful as we managed to disseminate the ER4STEM Framework, Generic Curricula and Repository beyond Bulgaria and the European Union. Furthermore, close contact with the teachers provided us with a good initial feedback on the Generic Curricula, which was still under construction.</p>

MOLDOVA ICT SUMMIT

Date	03/30/2017
------	------------

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

General Description	<p>At its 8th edition, Moldova ICT Summit 2017 is the leading industry event aimed to gather all industry stakeholders, including government, business, multinationals, professionals, educators and academia, to discuss trends and challenges facing the ICT industry globally and in the country, set the premises for sustainable entrepreneurship environment to foster innovation and attract investment. It focuses on bringing the most actual topics into discussion and showcases the top experiences from national and international experts.</p> <p>By bringing the cutting-edge global trends and inviting visionary leaders, the event seeks to break the barriers, drive innovation and foster higher aspirations at all levels. Going through an intense change from its first edition, MICT Summit 2017 will emphasize the development of the Republic of Moldova's ICT industry to enable an alignment to the global trends.</p> <p>Another particular direction which will enter into focus is ICT4Education where various aspects on Digital Education, latest solutions in education would be presented worldwide and in Moldova. It is planned to present the latest educational offer, the result of the pilot program and successful partnerships that are already started. Another accent that will be mentioned is improving Vocational ICT Education and Training (VET) Program, that are more and more developed and how this way should to continue.</p>
Multimedia	<p>https://www.facebook.com/pg/MoldovaICTsummit/photos/?tab=album&album_id=1360657240689407</p> <p>https://www.facebook.com/media/set/?set=a.1360761420678989.1073741853.100277590060718&type=1&l=5e07cf2faa</p> <p>https://www.facebook.com/pg/MoldovaICTsummit/photos/?tab=album&album_id=1361226143965850</p> <p>http://agora.md/stiri/30188/agora-recomanda-top-9-speakeri-pe-care-trebuie-sa-i-vezi-la-ict-summit-moldova</p>
Target Audience	Government, business, multinationals, professionals, educators and academia
Feedback / Impact	Generally the feedback received was good, but such a big audience did not allow for many questions and discussions. It was a good awareness initiative for the ER4STEM project.
Language	English / Romanian

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

Local/Global	International event in Chisinau, Moldova at Tekwill 9/11 Studenților Str.s
Organizer/Other involved parties	Tekwill
Activity Type	Presentation
URL	https://www.tekwill.md/events/moldova-ict-summit-2017
Comments/Summary	<p>The ER4STEM project was presented in front of a very large international audience and a strong focus was put on the importance of multidisciplinary activities, as such involving educational robotics, for cultivating 21st century skills. The previously conducted teacher workshop in Moldova was presented, as well as some data from the educational robotics workshops, to highlight the positive aspects of activities such as this one.</p> <p>A short presentation about the ER4STEM Generic Curricula, Framework and Repository was also included.</p>

TEACHERS' WORKSHOP AT ECER 2017

Date	11.04.2016
General Description	A workshop for the attending teachers of ECER 2017 in Sofia was carried out as replacement of the originally planned Scientix teachers panel workshop (see also D8.4).
Multimedia	
Target Audience	Teachers attending ECER
Feedback / Impact	The teachers were interested in getting knowledge about technologies usable for robotics workshops but also for possibly integrating them into actual school subjects such as mathematics.
Language	English
Local/Global	Local physical event in Sofia, Bulgaria
Organizer/Other involved parties	Organizers: ESI CEE and PRIA
Activity Type	Presentation and discussion about technologies and robotics platforms used in ER4STEM workshops (such as Hedgehog)

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

URL	
Comments/Summary	This event

KUYSTENDIL TEACHER AND STUDENTS' WORKSHOP

Date	05/11/2017 - 05/12/2017
General Description	ESI CEE was invited by Kuystendil Municipality to carry out a teacher and a students' workshop on educational robotics.
Multimedia	https://dariknews.bg/regioni/kiustendil/it-konferenciia-i-rabotilnica-po-robotika-za-uchenicite-v-kiustendil-2022765 https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bXerR-LgvfQ&feature=share https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ItMyaA2fKhk&feature=share https://www.facebook.com/plugins/post.php?href=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.facebook.com%2Fesicenter.bg%2Fposts%2F1827961164191285& https://www.facebook.com/plugins/post.php?href=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.facebook.com%2Fesicenter.bg%2Fposts%2F1826512454336156&
Target Audience	School students of age 9-14, and secondary or high school teachers
Feedback / Impact	<p>ESI CEE received positive feedback both from the students and the teachers.</p> <p>ESI CEE had to support teachers in overcoming technological fears and combat skepticism on why this will be useful for their classroom. Ultimately we managed to leave positive impact on them, and that now they know how the ER4STEM project could be of help to them, should they decide to include educational robotics in their classroom.</p>
Language	Bulgarian
Local/Global	<p>Local event in Kuystendil, Bulgaria at "ODK" Complex:</p> <p>16 "Marin Drinov" Str.</p>

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

Organizer/Other involved parties	Kuystendil Municipality European Software Institute – Center Eastern Europe (ESI CEE)
Activity Type	05/11/2017 – ER4STEM presentation and Teacher Workshop on the ER4STEM Educational Robotics and Creativity Workshop Activity Plan, including detailed orchestration of the activity, preparation of the materials, explaining how to install and run all necessary software, how to troubleshoot technology, where to buy replacements. Information about the ER4STEM Repository on Educational Robotics and the ER4STEM Generic Curriculum. 05/12/2017 – ER4STEM presentation Students Workshop under the ER4STEM Educational Robotics and Creativity Workshop Activity Plan. This workshop was included in the ER4STEM workshops in project year 2 and was standardly evaluated.
URL	https://dariknews.bg/regioni/kiustendil/it-konferenciia-i-rabotilnica-po-robotika-za-uchenicite-v-kiustendil-2022765
Comments/Summary	The event was successful as we got to listen to teacher’s needs and fears regarding STEM, and more specifically, educational robotics for STEM. Tutors got to understand how they might go about looking for an educational robotics activity and how, or more specifically, on what criteria would they choose and adapt an activity, such as this workshop. This will definitely be of use for the ER4STEM Generic Curricula, which is under development within WP2 of ER4STEM.

BIZZIT CONFERENCE 2017, KUYSTENDIL, BULGARIA

Date	05/13/2017
General Description	ESI CEE presented the ER4STEM project within the BizzIT Conference 2017. ESI CEE, also shared more information about the educational robotics workshops with teachers and students from Kuystendil, showed aggregated students’ feedback and photos to make a case on the use of educational robotics as a tool to support the general education process and the development of 21 st century skills. ESI CEE also did a robotics demonstration with the NAO robot and an interview with participating students and teachers

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

Multimedia	https://www.facebook.com/plugins/post.php?href=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.facebook.com%2Fgeorgi.prusiiski%2Fposts%2F10203108957920708&
Target Audience	Entrepreneurs, teachers, educators, local companies
Feedback / Impact	ESI CEE received positive feedback and had a few questions from the audience, mostly related to how do we see the future of educational robotics in Kuystendil and what could be done to make it more accessible for local students and teachers alike.
Language	Bulgarian
Local/Global	Local event in Hotel Kuystendil at: 19 "Kalosia" Str., Kuystendil, Bulgaria
Organizer/Other involved parties	Kuystendil Municipality and partners
Activity Type	Presentation, demonstration, interview
URL	https://www.facebook.com/events/1942769332635554/?active_tab=discussion
Comments/Summary	The event was successful for raising awareness about the ER4STEM project and for showing how it could bring benefit to the educational process. It was also a good opportunity to hear out relevant stakeholders and possible future users of the ER4STEM Generic Curricula, which is under development within WP2 of the ER4STEM project.

SUMMER SCHOOL IN ROBOTICS

Date	08/21/2017 - 08/26/2017
General Description	It is an annual educational robotics school that aims to inspire students to learn and use robotics. ESI CEE in cooperation with other tutors provided lessons to students, who did not have previous experience in engineering, using exercises

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

	<p>from two ER4STEM activity plans namely Educational Robotics and Creativity Workshop and Visualizing Mathematics with the MathBot. The team developed a scenario and programmed the Finch and Tank robots to complete a mission together with the other more experienced teams.</p>
Multimedia	n/a
Target Audience	2 teachers and a group of ten 8-18 years old female and male students
Feedback / Impact	<p>The teachers, who are specialized in teaching of mathematics, found the activities very useful and decided to try to initiate educational robotics programs to teach mathematics in their schools located in Pernik and Varna. They decided to further develop the activities during the 2018 edition of the initiative that will take place from the 20th August 2018 until the 25 of August 2018 at Oriyahovitsa, Bulgaria at the Minu Balkanski Foundation premises</p> <p>Ten students were excited to program Finch and ESI tank robots in a 5-day course.</p> <p><i>“Scouts (Tank and Finch robots used as a part of ER4STEM activity plans) were the smallest or less inexperienced, but they did not give in to the other teams. They had to work with the Scratch program and set Finch to make aliens-based observation and assessment and report to other mission participants.”</i> reported one of the team members in her authored article “ How I found friends among the robots” published in the online school newspaper.</p> <p>ESI CEE received valuable feedback that was used to further improve the activity plans.</p>
Language	Bulgarian
Local/Global	<p>Local event in Oriyahovitsa, Bulgaria at the Minu Balkanski Foundation premises;</p> <p>Oriyahovitsa 6061 Village, Stara Zagora Region, Bulgaria</p>
Organizer/Other involved parties	Minu Balkanski Foundation

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

Activity Type	Summer School in Robotics
URL	n/a
Comments/Summary	The event was very successful in terms of reaching the students and inspiring them to see STEM as a career or advanced studies option, but more importantly, we think it managed to show them the interconnectivity between STEM and other domains, such as music, arts, cooking. It was questionably successful when it came to motivating teachers to integrate robotics as an educational tool, but we did receive questions and positive feedback from them, as well as an invitation to return with a more focused talk for teachers.

SVETLINA PRIVATE SCHOOL PRESENTATION

Date	06/15/2017
General Description	ESI CEE was invited by Svetlina Private Schools to give a short inspirational talk on STEM in real life to motivate students to work harder in the STEM fields.

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

Multimedia	http://svetlina.net/%D1%83%D1%80%D0%BE%D1%86%D0%B8-%D1%81-%D0%BF%D0%BE%D0%B1%D0%B5%D0%B4%D0%B8%D1%82%D0%B5%D0%BB%D0%B8-2/
Target Audience	Primary and secondary school students, and potentially, their teachers.
Feedback / Impact	Children were very fascinated by robotics and by cyborgs, as well as the issues related to the ethics of cyborg humans. They were discussing, asking questions, reflecting on topics such as, if they could enhance themselves through robotics or sensors, what would they want to do or what would they do if they met a person with such enhancements. Afterwards, they were really surprised to find out that robotics is actually not a sci-fi field and that things like that exist. We discussed their interests and what they want to do and brainstormed about how robotics could be a part of their job of choice.
Language	Bulgarian
Local/Global	Local event in Sofia, Bulgaria in Svetlina Private Schools, at: 3 "Yozef Valdhard" Str., Sofia, Bulgaria
Organizer/Other involved parties	Svetilina Private Schools European Software Institute – Center Eastern Europe (ESI CEE)
Activity Type	Inspirational talk for primary and secondary school students in a private school.
URL	http://svetlina.net/%D1%83%D1%80%D0%BE%D1%86%D0%B8-%D1%81-%D0%BF%D0%BE%D0%B1%D0%B5%D0%B4%D0%B8%D1%82%D0%B5%D0%BB%D0%B8-2/
Comments/Summary	The event was very successful in terms of reaching the students and inspiring them to see STEM as a career or advanced studies option, but more importantly, we think it managed to show them the interconnectivity between STEM and other domains, such as music, arts, cooking. It was questionably successful when it came to motivating teachers to integrate robotics as an educational tool, but we did receive questions and positive feedback from them, as well as an invitation to return with a more focused talk for teachers.

GREECE – UOA

“ROBOTS AND EXPERIMENTS” WEEK - PART OF A SUMMER CAMP

Date	3-7 July 2017
General Description	<p>Educational Robotics Workshops were organized as part of a Summer Camp at the Industrial Gas Museum in Athens (July 2017). Each workshop had duration 4 hours and it was divided into 4 days (1 hour/day).</p> <p>Children were divided in 2 age groups: 6-8 and 9-12. The younger children built racing cars with Lego WeDo 2.0. And they had a racing competition on the last day. Older students used lego NXT kit to build and program a smart and autonomous robot (the activities were based on the activity plan ‘Build a robot and make it smart’)</p>
Multimedia	https://www.facebook.com/events/118264335421791/
Target Audience	Children (6-12 years old), Parents

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

Feedback / Impact	Children showed great enthusiasm with the robotic kits and especially with the construction part. For the young kids the racing competition was very motivating and they expressed intention to participate again in similar activities.
Language	Greek
Local/Global	The workshops were organized in the Technopolis City of Athens venue (http://www.technopolis-athens.com/web/guest/museum/home)
Organizer/Other involved parties	The workshops were organized by Educational Technology Lab UoA The summer camp was organized by Technopolis City of Athens, the Industrial Gas Museum, and ArtFygio center
Activity Type	Hands-on Workshops with Lego Wedo 2.0 and Lego NXT robotics kits
URL	Summer Camp Event: http://www.technopolis-athens.com/web/guest/events/~/eventsbrowser/16979/0/0/0?p_p_action=1&_bs_events_browser_loadaction=view&_bs_events_browser_eventStartDate=19%2F06%2F2017&_bs_events_browser_eventEndDate=14%2F07%2F2017&_bs_events_browser_redirect=%2Fweb%2Fguest%2Fevents%3Fp_p_id%3Dbs_events_browser%26p_p_action%3D0%26p_p_state%3Dnormal%26p_p_mode%3Dview%26p_p_col_id%3Dcolumn-2%26p_p_col_count%3D1%26_bs_events_browser_d-148316-p%3D4 Industrial Gas Museum website http://www.technopolis-athens.com/web/guest/museum/home
Comments/Summary	

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

3.3 ACTIVITIES WITHIN THE THIRD YEAR

AUSTRIA – TU WIEN

WORKSHOP FOR HIGH SCHOOL IN LARINO, ITALY

Date	22.12.2017
General Description	One of the researchers got married in 2017, so he and his wife decided to give a donation of two Thymio II to the high school in Larino-Italy. As a part of the donation a workshop was given to 24 participants, who were selected by the vice principal of the school.
Multimedia	10 Thymio and Laptops.
Target Audience	15-18 year old
Feedback / Impact	The feedback from the school was very positive, thankful and convinced to invite the TU Vienna again.
Language	Italian
Local/Global	Local (Student, media/press and teachers attended)
Organizer/Other involved parties	
Activity Type	A presentation about robotics was done at the beginning to show the participants the state of the art of robotics and then some exercises using the robots was done.
URL	http://www.moliseweb.it/info.php?id=12815&tit=La-scuola-si-apre-allo-studio-della-robotica:-il-22-Dicembre-al-Liceo-di-Larino-workshop-con-Julian-Angel-dell%27Universit%C3%A0-di-Vienna#sthash.5ox77ZYl.gbpl
Comments/Summary	Further information could be found on the activity plan created for this activity.

ISTITUTO SUPERIORE DI LARINO

ROBOT A SCUOLA

IL PROGETTO ER4STEM METTE A DISPOSIZIONE 10 ROBOT THYMIO II

WORKSHOP FORMATIVO PRESSO LA SEDE LICEALE

IL GIORNO 22 DICEMBRE DALLE ORE 8 15 ALLE 12 50

IL THYMIO TI PERMETTE DI CONOSCERE LA ROBOTICA IN MODO DIVERTENTE

er4stem QUESTO PROGETTO NASCE NELL'UNIVERSITA' DI VIENNA CON LO SCOPO DI INTRODURRE LO STUDIO DELLA ROBOTICA NELLE SCUOLE PRIMARIE E SECONDARIE

ATTIVITA'

- PRE QUESTIONARIO
- COSTRUIRE UN LABIRINTO
- MISURARE CON THYMIO
- IL MIO PRIMO PROGRAMMA CON ASBEA
- RISPONDERE AI COMANDI
- NON CADERE DAL TAVOLO!
- VAI AVANTI!
- ATTENZIONE E NON SCHIANTARSI!

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

PRESENTATION AT SABANA UNIVERSITY, BOGOTA- COLOMBIA

Date	16.03.2017
General Description	The presentation showed the work done during the first two years of the project, presenting the definition of stakeholders involved in Educational Robotics and the idea behind the framework.
Multimedia	
Target Audience	25+
Feedback / Impact	The feedback from the participants was positive, they really like the presentation and they would like to know more about the work done in the project.
Language	Spanish
Local/Global	Local (Master students from the technology education program and some professors)
Organizer/Other involved parties	Sabana University, Bogota- Colombia

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

Activity Type	Oral presentation in a Colombian University.
URL	
Comments/Summary	

Conferencia: Robótica educativa para STEM

PhD. Julián Ángel

Fecha: viernes 16 de marzo de 2018.
Hora: 4:00 p.m. - 5:30 p.m.
Lugar: auditorio K2,
Universidad de La Sabana.

Investigador asistente y coordinador científico del Proyecto Europeo sobre Robótica Educativa para STEM (European project Educational Robotics for STEM - ER4STEM), en la Universidad Técnica de Viena (Technical University of Vienna). Este proyecto busca generar un uso creativo de la robótica educativa incentivando la curiosidad de los niños en el mundo. Está hecho pensando en el uso crítico de la robótica para conectar metodologías pedagógicas con las habilidades del siglo XXI.

Entrada libre. Inscripciones abiertas. <http://bit.ly/2FSzk14>

LANGE NACHT DER FORSCHUNG (LONG NIGHT OF RESEARCH)

Date	13.04.2018
------	------------

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

General Description	This is an austrian event to show the general public the work done in research institutions.
Multimedia	10 Thymio and Laptops.
Target Audience	All
Feedback / Impact	
Language	German
Local/Global	Local (Student, media/press, kids and teachers attended)
Organizer/Other involved parties	Several organizations in Vienna
Activity Type	The exercise which has been presented was the maze design where a Thymio robot has to be guided threw with multiple presses in advance.
URL	https://www.langenachtderforschung.at/2018/index.html
Comments/Summary	

MAKER FAIRE 2018

Date	May, 06. 2018
General Description	As part of the workshop series at the „Maker Faire 2018“ we did a modified version of the workshop which takes less time and teaches the participants what robots and technology means. First thing has been a coding example on the robot Thymio to program a maze path into the robot via 4 direction buttons. After that we did a few exercises with assistance via a screen to show them quickly what the task is and only a small task for them to think about has been left over.
Multimedia	5 Laptops, 5 Mazes, 10 Thymios (only 5 needed, but it's good to have more for kids which are late)
Target Audience	8-12 years old
Feedback / Impact	The workshop has been great for the kids, they loved it and the tasks have been good to be solved for them. The date

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

	early in the morning is a little tricky how much participants are going to be there as they are not subscribed to any workshop and they come when the workshop starts.
Language	German
Local/Global	Local
Organizer/Other involved parties	TU Wien/ER4STEM
Activity Type	Simple programming via touchbuttons, programming with VPL in Thymio Studio
URL	https://makerfairevienna.com/workshop
Comments/Summary	Feedback on the workshop was very good. The only negative thing was that it's very unclear how much kids will attend as they just attend while they are on the maker faire with „first come first served“ principle. That's fixed from the organizers.

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

AUSTRIA – PRIA

EXHIBITION “ROBOTS DISCOVERY”, EUROPEAN ROBOTICS WEEK 2017

Date	27.03.2017
General Description	ER4STEM was invited to exhibit at the “Robots Discovery”, part of the European Robotics Week 2017, hosted by the Committee of Regions. Wilfried Lepuschitz from PRIA took part as representative from ER4STEM and presented the Hedgehog controller, which could be tried and programmed by the visitors.
Multimedia	
Target Audience	Citizens, representatives of the Committee of Regions
Feedback / Impact	Interested visitors were able to program the Hedgehog controller and thus understand the usability of robotics as tool for fostering children’s interest in STEM. A few local journalists also interviewed Wilfried Lepuschitz regarding ER4STEM and educational robotics in general (unfortunately no material could be obtained).
Language	English
Local/Global	Local physical event in Brussels, Belgium
Organizer/Other involved parties	Organizers: European Committee of the Regions
Activity Type	Exhibition
URL	https://www.eu-robotics.net/robotics_week/newsroom/press/30-projects-robots-discovery-exhibiton.html?changelang=4
Comments/Summary	The event was a good chance to present ER4STEM in general and Hedgehog in particular in the heart of the EU to citizens and to representatives of the Committee of Regions. Especially the latter was of interest as regional projects represent a suitable way of further broadening the impact of ER4STEM.

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

MALTA – ACROSLIMITS

No specific general activities to be reported for 3rd project year but ER4STEM is generally mentioned during meetings with stakeholders.

UK – CARDIFF UNIVERSITY

KIDSMEET CARDIFF

Date	6th July 2018
General Description	A dissemination and networking event for secondary school students and their teachers. Students from different schools delivered presentations on their work as Digital Leaders, with time for networking after each presentation. One of the schools had taken part in the Virtual Robotics workshop run by Cardiff University in ER4STEM, and so delivered a presentation on this work. Furthermore, the day opened with a presentation by Dr Carina Girvan on ER4STEM and the Virtual Robotics programme. Finally, the day closed with a session in the virtual world, learning how to programme SLurtles.
Multimedia	Multiple photos from the event and the publicity material can be found on the event’s twitter page: https://twitter.com/KidsMeetCardiff

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

Target Audience	<p>“Digital Leaders” - Secondary students in South Wales who lead and support their peers and teachers in using digital technology in their learning. These students attended with a teacher.</p> <p>“Digital Competency Framework Leads” - Secondary school teachers in charge of ensuring the ‘Digital Competency Framework’ curriculum is delivered at their school, who are interested in setting up Digital Leaders at their school.</p>
Feedback / Impact	<p>Two post-activity questionnaires were completed by attendees - one for the teachers and one for the students.</p> <p>Summary of teacher feedback: What they gained: Networking, ideas, how to engage pupils, how to set up digital leaders Improvement: More schools, students applying their ideas 100% answered that they would be interested in attending a similar event again.</p> <p>Summary of student feedback: They enjoyed: Networking, Presenting and Virtual Robotics Suggested improvements: More schools, more activities, longer time spent on the virtual world. 50% rated 4/5 and 50% rated 5/5</p> <p>Impact: One school included an article about the KidsMeet in their school newsletter.</p> <div data-bbox="639 983 1134 1608" style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px;"> <p>Cardiff University KidMeet</p> <p>Our Digital Leadership Team were invited to speak at a KidMeet conference earlier this month at Cardiff University. Our students shared their successful story as digital leads to 15 other schools who were in attendance and discussed ideas with 4 other groups of digital leaders who also presented from across the region. We are incredibly proud of our students for their hard work preparing for this event and for being an absolute credit to St. Martin's School throughout the day. They have truly dedicated themselves to this very important role this year and we look forward to the progress they make next year as school leaders.</p> <p>For those wishing to join our team, applications will reopen in September.</p> </div> <p>Enquiries from schools wishing to run Virtual Robotics in their schools next year.</p>
Language	English
Local/Global	Locally in South Wales, although there was a substantial amount of activity on Twitter.

Organizer/Other involved parties	Dr Carina Girvan and Sarah Hopkins-Weaver from Cardiff University in partnership with Becki Bawler from Risca Community Comprehensive School.
Activity Type	Demonstrations, presentations and networking
URL	https://twitter.com/KidsMeetCardiff https://sites.cardiff.ac.uk/curriculumsupport/activity/kidsmeet-cardiff-digital-leaders-event/
Comments/Summary	NA

<p>WHEN? Friday 6th July 2018 10:00 - 14:30</p> <p>WHERE? School of Social Sciences Glamorgan Building Cardiff University</p> <p>WHO? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Secondary school Digital Leaders and their teachers DCF leads Teachers interested in setting up digital leaders in their school </p> <p>REGISTER Contact us at: KidsMeet@cardiff.ac.uk <small>Please note that this event will be in the medium of English.</small></p>	
<p>At sylw pob Arweinydd Digidol!</p> <p>Hoffem eich gwahodd chi a'ch athrawon i'r KidsMeet cyntaf yn Mhrifysgol Caerdydd ar 6 Gorffennaf 2018. Yn KidsMeet byddwch yn cael cyfle i gryfhwyo'r gwaith sy'n cael ei wneud yn eich ysgol chi gyda thechnoleg digidol, ac i gwybod am beth mae arweinydd digidol eraill yn ei wneud yn eu hysgolion nhw. Cewch gyfle hefyd i ddyfysu am fyd rhithwir newydd ar gyfer roboteg! Gall hyd at 4 arweinydd digidol o bob ysgol ddod i'r digwyddiad ac mae'n rhaid i chi ddod â'ch athro neu athrawes.</p>	<p>At sylw pob Arweinydd Fframwaith Cymhwysedd Digidol mewn Ysgolion Uwchradd!</p> <p>Ydych chi'n ystyried penodi arweinydd digidol yn eich ysgol uwchradd? Dewch draw i KidsMeet i ddyfysu gan arweinydd digidol am y mathau o weithgareddau maen nhw'n eu cynnal. Staradwch ag athrawon sydd wedi cyflwyno arweinydd digidol a chwedd â setydidiadau ac academyddion eraill sy'n cynnal prosiectau digidol arloesol mewn ysgolion ac sy'n cyfrannu at ddatblygu a gwerthuso'r Fframwaith Cymhwysedd Digidol.</p>
<p>Calling all Digital Leaders!</p> <p>We would like to invite you and your teachers to the first KidsMeet at Cardiff University on the 6th July 2018. At KidsMeet you will have the opportunity to present about the work being done in your school using digital technology and hear about what other digital leaders are doing in their schools. You will also get an opportunity to explore a new virtual world for robotics! Up to 4 digital leaders from each school can attend and you must bring your teacher.</p>	<p>Calling all Secondary School DCF Leads!</p> <p>Are you thinking about introducing digital leaders into your secondary school? Come along to KidsMeet and learn from digital leaders about the types of activities that they do. Speak to teachers who have introduced digital leaders and meet with other organisations and academics who are running innovative digital projects in schools and involved with the development and evaluation of the DCF.</p>
<p>Diddordeb? Dim ond hyn a hyn o leodd sydd or gael! Cysylltwch â ni i gael rhagor o wybodoeth ac i gofrestru</p> <p>@KidsMeetCardiff KidsMeet@cardiff.ac.uk</p>	<p>Interested? Places are limited! Get in contact for more information and to find out how to register</p> <p>@KidsMeetCardiff KidsMeet@cardiff.ac.uk</p>
<p><small>Cynhelir y digwyddiad hwn gan Dr Carina Girvan a Yngol y Gwyddorau Cymdeithasol yn Mhrifysgol Caerdydd ac mae wedi'i gefnogi gan y prosiect Roboteg Adroddol ar gyfer STEM. Mwy o brosiectau hysbysu a'u nodwdd HORIZON 2020 yn Unioedd Ewropeaidd dan ychydig NIF 665972. Twfwrth y digwyddiad maent cyhoeddiad i Ms Bawler a Ysgol Risca Community Comprehensive School.</small></p>	<p><small>This event is hosted by Dr Carina Girvan from the School of Social Sciences at Cardiff University and is supported by the Educational Robotics for STEM project. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972. Twfwrth y digwyddiad maent cyhoeddiad i Ms Bawler a Ysgol Risca Community Comprehensive School.</small></p>

BULGARIA – ESI CEE

SVETLINA PRIVATE SCHOOL PRESENTATION AND SHORT WORKSHOP

Date	12/13/2017 – 12/14/2017
------	-------------------------

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

General Description	<p>This event was organized by Svetlina Private School and ESI CEE. The goal for the first day was to make a short presentation of ER4STEM and the topic of robotics in education in front of primary school students and their teachers. We also made a demonstration with the humanoid robot NAO. On the second day, we did a very short workshop with the Finch Robot by BirdBrain Technologies for secondary school students, and with the support and observance of their teachers. The goal was mainly for the teachers to see such activity in action with the idea to further start integrating simple robotics activities as part of their mathematics classes.</p>
Multimedia	<p>http://pedagogika.bg/2018/01/22/obrazovatelna-robotika-stem-obuchenie/</p> <p>https://www.facebook.com/pg/svetlinasofia/photos/?tab=album&album_id=1654484711239509</p>
Target Audience	Primary and secondary school students, and their teachers.
Feedback / Impact	<p>The feedback for both days was positive, especially from the students, who appreciated the activity. The teachers were able to ask questions and observe our work and several of them got excited. They were all made familiar with the educational robotics resources made available for use by the ER4STEM project and promised to contribute with their own activities to the ER4STEM repository.</p>
Language	Bulgarian
Local/Global	Local event in Sofia, Bulgaria in Svetlina Private Schools, at: 3 "Yozef Valdhard" Str., Sofia, Bulgaria
Organizer/Other involved parties	Svetilina Private Schools European Software Institute – Center Eastern Europe (ESI CEE)
Activity Type	Presentation, Short Workshop

URL	<p>http://pedagogika.bg/2018/01/22/obrazovatelna-robotika-stem-obuchenie/</p> <p>https://www.facebook.com/pg/svetlinasofia/photos/?tab=album&album_id=1654484711239509</p>
Comments/Summary	<p>The event was generally a very successful occasion to disseminate the ER4STEM project activities among Bulgarian teachers in a private school environment, where they have more flexibility to add new activities to their educational process. It was also a good occasion to demonstrate the ER4STEM Generic Curricula, which is under development in WP2 and get their feedback and use cases.</p>

WORLD SUMMIT AWARDS GLOBAL CONGRESS 2018

Date	03/20/2018 – 03/22/2018
------	-------------------------

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

General Description	<p>ESI CEE is the Bulgarian national coordinator of WSA. Two members of the team of ESI CEE were invited to participate in the Annual Global Congress of WSA. The World Summit Awards are a unique awards system, selecting and promoting local digital innovation with high impact on improving society. Combining an ongoing series of international events and activities with a global network of start-ups, social entrepreneurs, mentors, jurors, speakers, experts, government leaders, academia and civil society, WSA is an international platform for cut edge examples on how ICTs can have an impact on society.</p> <p>Running 15 years by now, WSA has become a quality seal for digital content with societal impact in over 180 participating countries.</p>
Multimedia	<p>https://www.worldsummitawards.org/wsa_events/wsa-global-congress-2018-key-participants/</p> <p>https://www.worldsummitawards.org/wsa-global-congress-2018-2/</p>
Target Audience	Start-ups, social entrepreneurs, mentors, jurors, speakers, experts, government leaders, academia and civil society
Feedback / Impact	The feedback received was positive, especially from young educators who make web-based solutions for education and social issues. They provided us with valuable feedback on the ER4STEM repository, framework and generic curricula and expressed willingness to stay updated with the project's development and results. They also got interested by the data presented and shared that data such as this will be of help to them for the development of future solutions and reaching out to people.
Language	English
Local/Global	Global Event in Vienna, Austria Vienna City Hall
Organizer/Other involved parties	ICNM Salzburg and Vienna, Austria United Nations

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

Activity Type	Networking, presentation
URL	https://www.worldsummitawards.org/about/
Comments/Summary	The global awards of the World Summit Awards presented a good chance for the ER4STEM team to connect with young people who have applications and web solutions related to education, including educational robotics, and make them aware of the ER4STEM project and its deliverables. The event raised awareness for the ER4STEM project among start-ups, social entrepreneurs, mentors, jurors, speakers and experts from a variety of fields, which will contribute to ER4STEM's recognition on a global level.

KUYSTENDIL STUDENT WORKSHOP

Date	05/18/2018
General Description	ESI CEE was invited by Kuystendil Municipality to carry out a students' workshop on educational robotics. The idea was to carry out a workshop with a robotics arm to improve the collaborative skills of students and furthermore to introduce local teachers to this educational robotics activity and give them the opportunity to support their students in an activity that was new for both the students and the teachers.
Multimedia	https://dariknews.bg/regioni/kiustendil/uchenici-se-obuchavat-s-robotizirana-ryka-v-rabotilnica-po-robotika-v-kiustendil-snimki-2097888
Target Audience	Students 10 – 14 years old and their teachers.
Feedback / Impact	Teachers asked to be kept up to date with the ER4STEM project developments and were happy to hear that all steps related to organizing an educational robotics workshop, from the design of the activity, through its implementation and evaluation, are described in an understandable generic process.
Language	Bulgarian

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

Local/Global	Local event in Kuystendil, Bulgaria at “ODK” Complex: 16 "Marin Drinov" Str.
Organizer/Other involved parties	Kuystendil Municipality Local Schools European Software Institute – Center Eastern Europe (ESI CEE)
Activity Type	ER4STEM presentation at a Students’ Workshop. The workshop was carried out under the ER4STEM Educational Robotics for Sustainability and Life Skills Activity Plan. This workshop was included in the ER4STEM workshops in project year 3 and was standardly evaluated.
URL	https://dariknews.bg/regioni/kiustendil/uchenici-se-obuchavat-s-robotizirana-ryka-v-rabotilnica-po-robotika-v-kiustendil-snimki-2097888
Comments/Summary	The event was assessed by very successful both by the organizers and the target audience. We got the chance to disseminate ER4STEM to teachers through working with students, which positively impacted their understanding on what ER4STEM educational robotics is. We had the chance to present to teachers the ER4STEM generic curricula and framework and we gave them some time within one of the breaks to browse through the ER4STEM repository on educational robotics activities.

BIZZIT CONFERENCE 2018, KUYSTENDIL, BULGARIA

Date	05/19/2018
General Description	ESI CEE presented the ER4STEM project within the BizzIT Conference 2018. ESI CEE, also shared more information about the educational robotics workshops with students from Kuystendil held within the previous day, showed aggregated students’ feedback and photos to make a case on the use of educational robotics as a tool to support the general education process and the development of 21 st century skills. ESI CEE also did a robotics demonstration with students who participated with the workshop from the previous day, and they played the waste separation

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

	game with four robotic arms robot in front of the conference audience. We also made an interview with some of the students.
Multimedia	https://dariknews.bg/regioni/kiustendil/novi-tehnologii-robotika-digitalno-izobrazitelno-izkustvo-na-it-konferenciia-v-kiustendil-2098040 http://focus-radio.net/%D1%81%D0%B2%D0%B5%D1%82%D0%BE%D1%81%D0%BB%D0%B0%D0%B2-%D0%B2%D0%B0%D1%81%D0%B8%D0%BB%D0%B5%D0%B2-%D0%BE%D0%B1%D1%89%D0%B8%D0%BD%D0%B0-%D0%BA%D1%8E%D1%81%D1%82%D0%B5%D0%BD%D0%B4%D0%B8%D0%B-%D1%89/
Target Audience	Entrepreneurs, teachers, educators, local companies, students
Feedback / Impact	The deputy mayor of the town of Kuystendil, shared that he was very inspired by what he saw within the workshop from the previous day, and promised that he and several of the teachers would work to organize a robotics club in Kuystendil. ESI CEE took the opportunity to share that ER4STEM provides a lot of resources that might make this task easier and stated that they are ready to further support the teachers by organizing teacher workshops and consultations.
Language	Bulgarian
Local/Global	Local event in Hotel Kuystendil at: 19 "Kalosia" Str., Kuystendil, Bulgaria
Organizer/Other involved parties	Kuystendil Municipality and partners
Activity Type	Presentation, demonstration, interview

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

URL	http://www.kyustendil2018.bizzit.org/ https://www.facebook.com/100011561431662/videos/529618860766824/
Comments/Summary	ESI CEE received positive feedback and had a few questions from the audience, mostly related to how do we see the future of educational robotics in Kuystendil and what could be done to make it more accessible for local students and teachers alike.

DIGITAL AMBASSADORS BULGARIA – FIRST MEETING, WORKSHOP AND AWARDS

Date	05/28/2018 – 05/29/2018
General Description	<p>This event was organized by the Digital National Alliance /DNA/ which is part of the initiative of the European Commission Digital Skills and Jobs Coalition. The main goal of the alliance is to attract more young people to STEM, and to reach a more effective use of the digital potential, especially in the field of education.</p> <p>Over 100 teachers from all over Bulgaria have applied for the competition “Digital Ambassadors in class”, organized by the Digital National Alliance (DNA), with the support of the Ministry of Education and Science and Google.org. Special jury of DNA and Ministry of Education and Science representatives, academia and NGOs has evaluated the most innovative educational practices.</p> <p>12 teachers from different regions of Bulgaria, some of them Scientix Ambassadors have been selected for Digital Ambassadors. In the upcoming months, they will work to promote digital technologies in class, and support trainings of teachers in Northwest Bulgaria.</p> <p>This was their first meeting, and was organized within the Cybersecurity Laboratory at Sofia Tech Park. During the second day of the meeting, ESI CEE briefly demonstrated the humanoid robot NAO, showed workshop pictures and provided more information about the ER4STEM project.</p>
Multimedia	http://www.digitalteachers.eu/index.php/2018/06/28/digitalen_poslanik-3/
Target Audience	Teachers, government

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

Feedback / Impact	Many of the teachers naturally became interested in how they can benefit from the ER4STEM project. Within the networking part of the event, ESI CEE was available and answered their questions in a very informal setting, showed them the ER4STEM repository and the ER4STEM Generic Curricula and obtained their feedback. We also exchanged contacts and we are keeping them up to date with educational robotics activities.
Language	Bulgarian
Local/Global	Local physical event at the Laboratory Complex at Sofia Tech Park 111-B "Tsarigradsko Shosse" Blvd.
Organizer/Other involved parties	Ministry of Education and Science, Google.org with the support of the Cybersecurity Lab @ Sofia Tech Park
Activity Type	Demonstration, Networking
URL	http://www.digitalteachers.eu/
Comments/Summary	This was a great opportunity to disseminate the ER4STEM project in front of a targeted audience that will benefit from using the ER4STEM framework, repository and generic curriculum.

Date	08/20/2018 - 08/20/2018
General Description	It is an annual educational robotics school that aims to inspire students to learn and use robotics. Based on the success achieved in 2017 edition of the school ESI CEE in cooperation with other tutors provided lessons to students, who did not have previous experience in engineering, using exercises from two ER4STEM activity plans namely Educational Robotics and Creativity Workshop and Visualizing Mathematics with the MathBot. The team developed a scenario and programmed the Finch and Tank robots to complete a mission together with the

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

	other more experienced teams.
Multimedia	n/a
Target Audience	3 teachers and a group of fifteen 8-16 years old female and male students
Feedback / Impact	<p>The teachers, who are specialized in teaching of mathematics, found the activities very useful and decided to try to initiate educational robotics programs to teach mathematics in their schools located in Nova Zagora and Sofia. The organizers decide to include ER4STEM approach and activity plans as a part of the initiative in the next years.</p> <p>Ten students were very excited to program Finch and ESI tank robots in a 5-day course.</p>
Language	Bulgarian
Local/Global	<p>Local event in Oriyahovitsa, Bulgaria at the Minu Balkanski Foundation premises;</p> <p>Oriyahovitsa 6061 Village, Stara Zagora Region, Bulgaria</p>
Organizer/Other involved parties	Minu Balkanski Foundation
Activity Type	Summer School in Robotics
URL	

<p>Comments/Summary</p>	<p>The event was very successful in terms of reaching the students and inspiring them to see STEM as a career or advanced studies option, but more importantly, we think it managed to show them the interconnectivity between STEM and other domains, such as music, arts, cooking. It was questionably successful when it came to motivating teachers to integrate robotics as an educational tool, but we did receive questions and positive feedback from them, as well as an invitation to return with a more focused talk for teachers.</p>
-------------------------	---

GREECE – UOA

Participation and dissemination of the project’s progress in “Europe in a changing world - Information Day and Brokerage Event” that took place in Brussels, 14 November 2017. <https://ec.europa.eu/research/index.cfm?pg=events&eventcode=3952FF12-CDAB-800B-24B22C15EBE38D24>

Participation and dissemination of the project’s progress in “Horizon 2020 - Science with and for Society 2018” that took place in Brussels, 29th January 2018. <https://horizon-swafs2018.b2match.io/>

“ROBOTS AND MACHINES” WORKSHOPS - PART OF A SUMMER CAMP

<p>Date</p>	<p>2-6 July 2018</p>
-------------	----------------------

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

General Description	Two 4-hour Educational Robotics Workshops were organized as part of a Summer Camp at the Industrial Gas Museum in Athens (July 2017). The workshops were divided into 4 days (1 hour/day) and there were 110 kids participated. 65 of the kids attended the 1st workshop for younger kids in which they used Lego WeDo 2.0. The rest 45 of them attended the second workshop in which they constructed a robot with Lego NXT. The NXT workshops were based on the ER4STEM activity plans: 'Constructing and controlling a robot painter' (Year 1) and 'Building a robot and making it smart' (Year 3). In addition there was an introductory presentation about the ER4STEM project.
Multimedia	https://gasmuseum.gr/index.php/dimiourgiki-mathisi/summer-camp-stin-technopoli
Target Audience	Children (6-12 years old), Parents
Feedback / Impact	
Language	Greek
Local/Global	The workshops were organized in the Technopolis City of Athens venue (http://www.technopolis-athens.com/web/guest/museum/home)
Organizer/Other involved parties	The workshops were organized by Educational Technology Lab UoA The summer camp was organized by Technopolis City of Athens, the Industrial Gas Museum, and ArtFygio center
Activity Type	Hands-on Workshops with Lego Wedo 2.0 and Lego NXT robotics kits
URL	Summer Camp Event: http://www.technopolis-athens.com/web/guest/events/~/eventsbrowser/17470/7202/0/0?p_p_action=1&_bs_events_browser_loadaction=view&_bs_events_browser_eventStartDate=18%2F06%2F2018&_bs_events_browser_eventEndDate=13%2F07%2F2018&

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

	<p>bs_events_browser_redirect=%2Fweb%2Fguest%2Fevents%2F~%2Ftopic%2F7202&</p> <p>Industrial Gas Museum website</p> <p>http://www.technopolis-athens.com/web/guest/museum/home</p>
Comments/S ummary	

Photos from the 1st workshop:

Photos from the 2nd workshop:

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

4 WEB AND SOCIAL MEDIA DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

For the project, a website was established with the most relevant information: <http://er4stem.com/>

Also a Facebook profile was created, which regularly showed news: <https://www.facebook.com/er4stem/>

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

 Er4stem shared a post. ⋮

Published by

One of the workshop being held in Malta by [AcrossLimits \(Malta\)](#) as part of our research project for the [EU Code Week Malta](#) in collaboration with [ESkills Malta Foundation](#)

[EU Code Week Malta](#) Like Page

57230314300/1366567 ·

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

All partners generally provided links to ER4STEM on their websites and posted regularly news through their own channels. The following sections give an exemplary overview of these web and social media activities by the partners.

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

AUSTRIA – TU WIEN

The Vision for Robotics' webpage has a link to the project and activities done by TU Wien in the frame of the project are also presented. Some of the events were presented in the group's news page: <https://www.acin.tuwien.ac.at/en/vision-for-robotics/news-und-veranstaltungen/>

AUSTRIA – PRIA

PRIA shows the project on its website: <https://pria.at/education/projects/>

Activities of the project (especially ECER) are constantly mentioned at PRIA's Facebook page. A number of posts have therefore been related to ER4STEM: <https://www.facebook.com/PRIARobotics/>

MALTA – ACROSSLIMITS

AcrossLimits disseminates the project on the company's website (<http://acrosslimits.com/er4stem/>) and also during presentations.

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

 acrosslimits HOME WHO ARE WE? MEET THE TEAM OUR EXPERTISE PROJECTS

PROJECTS

Our European projects focus on a variety of innovative sectors – technology, education, entrepreneurship, health and social issues. We participate in research programmes (Horizon2020), educational programmes (Erasmus+) and also regional development programmes (Interreg Italia-Malta). We have been in projects since 2001 and are always glad to join more! Here are our current list of active projects.

 100 MIRRORS INCLUSIVE				
Innovative Open Data Education and Training based on PBL and Learning Analytics	Social Enterprise Skills for Business Advisers	Reading Early School Leaving Signals	Educational Robotics for Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics	100 Mirrors Inclusive Tools for the Motivation of Enterprising Disabled Women

 acrosslimits HOME WHO ARE WE? MEET THE TEAM OUR EXPERTISE PROJECTS

Educational Robotics for Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics

Project Acronym: ER4STEM
Project Full Name: Educational Robotics for Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics
Duration: 2015-2018
Sector: Robotics Education
Programme: Horizon 2020

The project has been mentioned in the AcrossLimits Newsletter edition 39 in May 2016. This newsletter is sent to approximately 10,000 people across Europe. <http://us9.campaign-archive1.com/?u=64faef28956805c079b27da13&id=774925957f>

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

AcrossLimits Newsletter #39 – May 2016

[View this email in your browser](#)

All things seem possible in May

Dear friends,

It's already the start of the fifth month of this year, and honestly, I have no idea how time has flown! Maybe as we age, it is indeed possible that time speeds up, or maybe I'm just really high from all the great things happening! :-)

List of courses provided by TrainingMalta and AcrossLimits

ER4STEM Workshops, Repository and More!

If you had to build your own robot what would you ask it to do? This H2020 project has been keeping our staff very busy! Following an expression of interest that was issued a few weeks ago in Malta, we not only met with different schools, but will be starting workshops in Primary Schools very soon, with more to follow in the next scholastic year! During the ER4STEM workshops, our team will be introducing robots, programming, solving mathematical problems and also letting the students be creative!

For our wider stakeholders (teachers, educators, researchers and robotics organisations), here at AcrossLimits, we have been brainstorming on the repository which will serve as a tool to help and facilitate the use of robotics as an educational tool.

We would like to invite you to follow the project [Facebook page](#), for further updates and news about robotics!

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

The project is constantly mentioned on our AcrossLimits and Training Malta Facebook pages. A number of posts have been shared dedicated to the project.

<https://www.facebook.com/acrosslimits/>

<https://www.facebook.com/TrainingInMalta>

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

During 2018 AcrossLimits has moreover held 2 Scientix online webinars in collaboration with all the partners of the project in January and February. A full report on these is available in deliverable D5.4.

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

Er4stem
Published by Annalise Duca [?] · 12 January ·

Places are filling up for next week [#webinar](#). Join us to learn how you can also use robotics in the classroom - <https://goo.gl/forms/WhrJfjxoABiZ8DC93>

ER4STEM - Repository Workshop (Webinar)

This online webinar is an hour session where the ER4STEM partners will be explaining the use of the ER4STEM repository. During this session we will be talking about activity plans, the framework and how an educator can make use of robotics across different subjects. This webinar contains a hand-on session and is in English.

Please fill in this form if you would like to book your slot. You can choose from 2 different dates. Limited places available.

For any questions, you can email us on er4stem@acrosslimits.com

**Required*

DOCS.GOOGLE.COM
ER4STEM - Repository Workshop (Webinar)
This online webinar is an hour session where the ER4STEM partners will...

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

 AcrossLimits (Malta) shared a video.
Published by

Join us on the 16th or the 22nd January for a webinar on one of our projects **Er4stem**. Learn about how you can use **#robotics** in your **#classroom**! Tag **#educators** and those who have learning close to their heart ❤️ 😊 **#education #er4stem #euprojects**

ER4STEM - Repository Webinar [Sign Up](#)

[UK – CARDIFF UNIVERSITY](#)

Tweets from lead researcher and school teachers about SLurtle workshops in schools. Tweets from dedicated Twitter account @KidsMeetCardiff about event and retweets of tweets from teachers about the day.

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

 Dr Carina Girvan
@cgirvan

1st #SLurtleRobotics in #virtualworld completed at #OakFieldPrimary today. Children, teachers & researchers learned SO much frm each other 🐢

5:22 PM - 12 May 2017 from Cardiff, Wales

The collage contains four images: 1. A certificate from '4stem' that says 'Congratulations! is a SLurtle world explorer' with fields for 'Signed' and 'Date'. 2. A screenshot of a virtual world showing a green turtle with a red square drawn around it. 3. A screenshot of a code editor showing a script: 'when I am touched', 'pen down', 'repeat 4', 'move 2 meters', 'turn 90 degrees'. 4. A screenshot of a code editor showing a script: 'when I am touched', 'pen down', 'repeat 5', 'move 2 meters', 'turn 90 degrees'.

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

 RCCS Science
@RCCS_Science Follow ▼

[@RCCS_MissBawler](#) Can we try this please ?
[#KidsMeetCardiff](#)

1:35 PM - 6 Jul 2018

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

[BULGARIA – ESI CEE](#)

The information about the ER4STEM project is uploaded and regularly maintained on the web page <http://esirobot.org/>. This page was designed and developed by ESI CEE within a previously implemented EU project.

The team of ESI CEE published on occasion on ESI CEE's Facebook information, pictures and videos about some of the activities performed within ER4STEM project: <https://www.facebook.com/esicenter.bg/>.

ESI CEE also published posts of the ER4STEM Facebook page: <https://www.facebook.com/er4stem>

Sample posts are illustrated in the screenshots below.

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

ESI European Software Institute-Center Eastern Europe
December 16, 2016 at 7:13 PM · 🌐

Today we had a visit from our youngest robo-enthusiasts. 😊 Not older than the age of 6, those kids know all about sensors, motors and humanoids 😊 Being so curious and intuitive about technology, asking spot-on questions and having super... 😊 [See More](#)

7 3 Shares

ESI European Software Institute-Center Eastern Europe share...
January 22 at 12:24 PM · 🌐

We have more than 100 people signed for the [Er4stem's](#) educational #robotics repository #webinar today Jan 22, 2018, 4PM CET! If you aren't... [See More](#)

Er4stem's Post
Are you a teacher struggling to keep your students motivated?...

👍 Dimitar Ivanov, Annalise Duca and Er4stem

ESI European Software Institute-Center Eastern Europe
August 29, 2016 at 6:18 PM · 🌐

...ESI CEE is warming up for the new set of educational robotics workshops for STEM, under the [Er4stem](#) project. For this school year, we have prepared a whole new workshop with the "Mathbot", using the Fi...

👍 Станислав Георгиев, Lara Lammer and 6 others 1 Share

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

ESI European Software Institute-Center Eastern Europe
May 5, 2016 at 2:11 PM · 🌐

Two incredibly talented 9-year-olds drew us a scientist yesterday minutes after the free educational robotics workshop within the [Er4stem](#) project. 😊 #scientists #educationalrobotics

Anna-Marie Vilamovska, Wilfried Lepuschitz and 3 others · 4 Shares

ESI European Software Institute-Center Eastern Europe
August 29, 2016 at 6:18 PM · 🌐

...ESI CEE is warming up for the new set of educational robotics workshops for STEM, under the [Er4stem](#) project. For this school year, we have prepared a whole new workshop with the "Mathbot", using the Fi...

Станислав Георгиев, Lara Lammer and 6 others · 1 Share

Er4stem
April 15, 2016 at 1:03 PM · 🌐

ER4STEM in #Bulgaria by @European Software Institute-Center Eastern Europe: Hands-on presentation to #students and #teachers @Varna Free... [See More](#)

ER4STEM / Роботите в образованието
www.youtube.com

Angele Giuliano, Lara Lammer and 2 others

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

 European Software Institute-Center Eastern Europe is at i...
March 11, 2017 at 7:07 PM · Chisinau, Moldova ·

So, during the last few days, we had the opportunity to share the experience we have gained so far during the course of the **Er4stem** project in front of an audience of 30 pedagogues and specialists from more than 10 educational institutions in Moldova. We... [See More](#)

 Мария Гаристова, Зоя Гълъбова and 3 others 2 Shares

 Er4stem
April 15, 2016 at 1:08 PM ·

Ivaylo Gueorguiev from [@European Software Institute-Center Eastern Europe](#) talking about **ER4STEM** at the [@Varna Free University "Chernorizets...](#) [See More](#)

Роботика и скрач - проект ER4STEM
www.youtube.com

 European Software Institute-Center Eastern Europe share...
May 26, 2017 at 2:10 PM · Sofia ·

It was a great honor for us last month to be the local coordinators for Bulgaria of the ECER 2017 – **European Conference on Educational Robotics**... [See More](#)

PRIA | Practical Robotics Institute Austria's Post
Many photos of the ECER 2017 in Sofia, Bulgaria will be posted...

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

ESI European Software Institute Center Eastern Europe
April 13, 2016 at 12:34 PM · 🌐

We're currently in Vienna, Austria at the [European Conference on Educational Robotics - ECER 2016](#). On this photo you can see one of the two Bulgarian teams, the team from Sofia Vocational High School of Electronics "John Atanasoff" / Софийска... [See More](#)

👍 Wilfried Lepuschitz, PRIA | Practical Robotics Institute Austria and 3 others

ESI European Software Institute Center Eastern Europe
April 25, 2017 at 12:24 AM · 🌐

A big #wow #welcome to all 200+ students from 43 teams from Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Iran, Kuwait, Malta and Poland and their teachers and mentors at ECER 2017 today! Such an honor having all of you here, guys! Thank you for coming... 😊 [See More](#)

👍 Er4stem, Daniel Maximilian Swoboda and 10 others 1 Comment 4 Shares

ESI European Software Institute Center Eastern Europe
May 12, 2017 at 11:52 PM · 🌐

...Bulgaria doing educational robotics workshop for both teachers and students under the [Er4stem](#) project. We're having a lot of fun, as always, and we're... [See More](#)

„Работилница по роботика” за най-младите в Кюстендил
www.youtube.com

👍 Снежина Машева and Веселина Спасова

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

ESI European Software Institute-Center Eastern Europe
October 21, 2016 at 6:10 PM · 🌐

Every week is #EUCodeWeek for us here at the **European Software Institute-Center Eastern Europe**! For the past 8-9 months, within the #er4stem project, we've been coding and constructing #Arduino robots with 550+ children aged 6-17 to channel their... 😊 See More

👍 Aleksandrov Milen and Веселина Спасова 4 Shares

ESI European Software Institute-Center Eastern Europe
May 15, 2017 at 2:42 PM · 🌐

...efforts at the **European Software Institute-Center Eastern Europe** and the Er4stem project to maintain children's motivation to study #STEM... See More

Кюстендил - работилница за роботи
www.youtube.com

👍 Биляна Йорданова and Снежина Машева

ESI European Software Institute-Center Eastern Europe
May 6 at 9:22 PM · 🌐

We are really proud to having had the honor of being a part of #ECER and the Er4stem project for yet another year ❤️ Check out some impressions... 😊 See More

ECER 2018
www.youtube.com

👍 Биляна Йорданова, Clemens Koza and 4 others

GREECE – UOA

We uploaded in youtube a video made from students that participated in the workshops of 7th High School of Trikala. In the video the students show their constructions and the robots they built (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=QICjSkR55YE>). This video was also shared at the official Facebook page of ETL (Educational Technology Lab).

We shared ER4STEM videos and posts at the official Facebook page of ETL. <https://www.facebook.com/educationaltechnologylab/?fref=ts>

We created and uploaded a video for the ER4STEM workshops that were organized in the 5th high school of Ilion. The video shows students working with robots during the workshop and the robotics artefacts they create. It also includes parts from the interviews where students express their opinion about STEM and robotics. The video includes episodes of collaboration, construction, testing, self-assessment and innovation. It is in greek but with English subtitles. The video was presented in the

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

school in the end of school year and it was also distributed through social media (facebook, youtube)
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nI2DoizG2vg&list=PLuCHavig2FzdClxvVpu0JiP6f9XMmg36I>

5 CONCLUSION

This document gives an overview on the non-scientific dissemination activities related to the project ER4STEM. As can be seen, the project was communicated on various types of events by all partners, even in countries not being a home country of any of the partners. In total ER4STEM was promoted in more than 40 activities in more than 10 countries. Besides, the project was presented in multiple web and social media activities. Also Scientix was used for disseminating ER4STEM but details on this channel can be found in deliverables D8.4 and D5.4.

The ER4STEM project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972